

Supplementary Material for Review

Materials and Methods

Mice

C57BL/6 mice were purchased from CLEA Japan (Tokyo, Japan). Mice carrying floxed alleles for STAT3 (STAT3^{fl/fl} mice) (1) were bred with CCSPrtTA/tetO-Cre mice (2) to establish mice with AEC-specific and DOX-dependent deletion of STAT3 [CCSPrtTA/tetO-Cre STAT3^{fl/fl} mice (STAT3-cKO)]. CCSPrtTA STAT3^{fl/fl} mice (STAT3-WT) were used as genetic control mice. STAT3-cKO mice and STAT3-WT mice were provided with DOX (625 mg/kg)-containing feed (CLEA Japan) from 2 weeks before the initiation of experiments to the end of experiments (3, 4). All mice were housed in microisolator cages under specific pathogen-free conditions. All experiments were approved by the Chiba University Animal Care and Use Committee.

HDM-induced allergic inflammation model

Mice were anesthetized as described previously (5) and then sensitized intratracheally (i.t.) twice with HDM extracts (50 µg, *D. Pteronyssinus*, Greer Laboratories, Lenoir, NC) in PBS at a 7-day interval. Seven days after the last sensitization, the mice were challenged i.t. with 10 µg of HDM extracts in PBS as indicated in Fig. 1A. Forty-eight hours after the last challenge, the numbers of eosinophils and CD4⁺ T cells recovered in bronchoalveolar lavage fluid (BALF) were evaluated by FACS analysis as previously described (6). Data were collected with FACSCanto II (BD Biosciences, San Diego, CA) and analyzed by FlowJo software (Tree Star, San Carlos, CA). For histological analysis, the lung was perfused with PBS to remove blood cells and was fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) phosphate buffer solution overnight.

Isolation of lung epithelial cells

Lung epithelial cells were isolated by two-step purification as previously described (7). In brief, lung cell suspensions were prepared by using Dispase (1000 PU/ml, GODO SHUSEI, Tokyo, Japan), and then CD45⁺ cells were depleted by magnetic sorting (MojoSort; BioLegend, San Diego, CA). Enriched CD45⁻ cells were subjected to further purification of club cell-rich fraction and alveolar epithelial type II (A₂II) cell-rich fraction by a cell sorter SH800Z (Sony Biotechnology, Tokyo, Japan) as described elsewhere (8). The resultant cells were >95% pure by flow cytometry.

Antibodies

The antibodies used for FACS analysis of BALF cells and for isolation of lung epithelial cells by FACS sorting were shown in Table S1 and Table S2, respectively.

Histological analysis

PFA-fixed lung sections (3 μm-thick, 4 sections per lung) were stained with hematoxylin-eosin (HE) and periodic acid-Schiff (PAS) according to standard protocols. Histopathological scoring and quantification of goblet cells were performed on HE- and PAS-stained lung sections, respectively in a blinded manner as previously described (9-11).

RNA-sequencing (RNA-seq) analysis

Total RNA was extracted from isolated cells by using a TRIzol reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. RNA-seq libraries were prepared using a NEBNext Ultra II Directional RNA Library Prep Kit (New England Biolabs, Ipswich, MA). RNA-seq was performed on NextSeq 500 (Illumina, San Diego, CA) using a NextSeq 500/550 High Output Kit v2.5 (Illumina) with a single 75 base-pair read. Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were identified as adjusted *p*-value < 0.05 using DESeq2 package (12) in R. Gene enrichment analyses

were performed using Metascape (<https://metascape.org/gp/index.html>) (13).

Effect of an SCD1 inhibitor on HDM-induced allergic inflammation

To inhibit SCD1 activity during HDM-induced allergic inflammation, 25 µg of A939572 (Cayman Chemical) in 250 µl of 10% DMSO in PBS or vehicle was administered intraperitoneally (i.p.) daily from day 0 to day 19.

Statistical analysis

Data are summarized as means ± SEM. The statistical analyses of the results were performed using Prism 9 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA). The respective statistical analyses are specified in each figure legend. P values <0.05 were considered significant.

References

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Supplementary Tables

Table S1. The antibodies for FACS analysis of BALF cells

Target molecule	Clone	Distributor
CD3 ϵ	145-2C11	BioLegend
CD4	RM4-5	BioLegend
CD8 α	53-6.7	BioLegend
CD11c	N418	BioLegend
CD19	1D3	BD Biosciences
Siglec-F	E50-2440	BD Biosciences

Table S2. The antibodies for isolation of lung epithelial cells by FACS sorting

Target molecule	Clone	Distributor
CD45	30-F11	BioLegend
CD31	MEC13.3	BioLegend
CD326 (EpCAM)	G8.8	BioLegend
I-A/I-E	M5/114.15.2	BioLegend